

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE CONTEXT OF FOREIGN STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

The study of inclusive education is one of the new, most pressing problems in the field of pedagogy. This article analyzes the content and features of the concept of "inclusive education", approaches to the problem of inclusive education.

Keywords: *inclusion, inclusive education, integration, socialization, integrated education, adaptation, ideology of inclusion.*

The study of inclusive education is one of the new, most pressing problems in the field of pedagogy. Based on the study of research on the problem, their scientific analysis, it became clear that the educational environment of young people with disabilities should always be good, moderate, always with special attention, not left out of sight of adults for the integration of every child into society.

Scientific theories and directions based on experiments related to the psychological characteristics of a person arose in Western Europe and the USA. Despite different interpretations of the mental nature of a person, these theories to a certain extent contributed to the development of the educational psychology of children with disabilities. In this regard, one can recognize the scientific research of J.Bruner [3], J.Piaget [11], A.Wallon [12], S.Hall [13], K.Buhler [4], E.Durkheim [5], D.Locke [8] and others.

The analysis shows that the gradual transition of foreign countries to inclusive education is associated with a change in society's attitude towards children with disabilities, increased attention to their education and the level of development.

Inclusive education - derived from the English word inclusive, inclusion - means to harmonize, involve, inclusive, and in Latin - to include, involve, that is, to overcome barriers between children with special needs and ordinary ones.. Inclusive education is one of the issues that have risen to the level of public policy. It is an educational system that is an inclusion in the learning process aimed at adapting to

social life, regardless of the developmental characteristics or economic difficulties faced by adolescents who need special attention.

The concept of "inclusive education" is considered in foreign literature from different positions:

as a philosophical category, its fundamental foundations are the recognition by society and the school of the uniqueness and dignity of each child, regardless of individual differences (A.Renzaglia) [9];

as a full and adequate interaction of students with disabilities and their peers, as well as teachers in the educational process and in extracurricular activities in secondary schools (D.L.Voltz) [15];

as an educational process and practice that provides the necessary support in general education schools located near the place of residence (R.Arends, C.A.Kochar, L.L.West, J.M.Taymans, Y.R.Shemesh) [1];

as the only natural learning environment in which all children learn on the basis of a single curriculum, the necessary support is provided to children with disabilities directly in the general classroom, all children are recognized as unique and accepted by each other, planning and implementation educational strategies are implemented by the student team (D.L.Ryndak, L.Jackson, F.Bilingsley) [10];

as an integral part of the modern educational paradigm, which has its own mission, philosophy, values, methods and activities, is understood as the basis of the organization within the school, its goals, system of views and daily activities (H.Levin) [6];

as an optimized and widely integrated integration of children with disabilities in secondary schools, it is not seen as an obstacle in the process, but as the starting point and goal of all pedagogical activity (A.Sander) [14];

"Inclusive" and "integration" are two stages of the same process, in which the needs of special education form the basis of all pedagogy (T.Booth, M. Ainscow, D.Kingstone) [2].

Identification of the most important features of inclusive education allows the author to define the concept of "inclusive education" from the point of view of axiological, cultural and procedural approaches. "Inclusive education is a multifaceted pedagogical phenomenon, which is based on the recognition of the identity, dignity and diversity of all children and the elimination of all forms of discrimination, the effective integration of each child into the general education system" [7].

World experience shows that the development of an inclusive education system as a form of integration of children with special educational needs is a long-term strategy that requires patience and tolerance, consistency, phased approach and an integrated approach to its implementation. However, in the broadest sense, integration (lat. integratio - connection) is a process of development, achieving unity and integrity within a system based on the interdependence of its individual specialized elements [18].

According to N.N.Malofeev, real integration in the upbringing of children with special needs involves the creation of optimal conditions for each child in general education institutions [19].

According to V.V.Kurkunov, anomalous children receive more external incentives for development in co-education, taking into account the creation of adequate learning conditions for children with disabilities [17].

R.Dimenstein and I.Larikova emphasize that one of the main aspects of integrated education is the right direction of education for a particular child. This direction does not depend on the form of organization of the educational process, the type of class, group, school in which the child is currently located. A child can be guided along the path of integration in a variety of ways, but it is important that each stage enhances his or her integration potential. Increasing the integration potential of the environment includes the training and retraining of teachers, special work with parents. These organizational, educational and pedagogical activities are aimed at increasing the integration potential of the educational institution and the system as a whole [16].

Thus, inclusion is the leading trend of the current stage of development of the education system, which does not contradict the principle of holistic learning in the system of general and special education. As a result, a child with special educational needs should enjoy the right to education in any type of educational institution and receive the necessary specialized assistance.

Education performs two major civilizational functions of personality development: its spiritual, moral, artistic, cultural development and socialization, as well as its economic function - the reproduction of qualified labor resources for social production.

According to A.Yu.Shemanov, in the modern cultural space there are two approaches to the problem of inclusive education. The first approach is based on the social model of understanding others and protecting their rights, including protection

from discrimination. The motto of this approach is to approach the problem of others here from the point of view of the methodology of social constructivism, which allows criticizing society, purposefully changing it and actively influencing public policy, despite differences in the cultural world and their values [20].

It should be noted that the social model of inclusion can serve as the object of its own criticism. Firstly, helping others involved in the learning process is not always acceptable (for example, these may be children with visual, hearing and mental retardation). Secondly, the very ideology of inclusiveness implies that people are “normal” but otherwise disabled and incompetent, which undermines the idea of community, solidarity and equality of groups.

From the above considerations, it must be concluded that all children can succeed if they receive the necessary support. This makes it possible to communicate in an atmosphere of empathy, tolerance, social justice and cooperation. In the future, successful socialization and education of children with disabilities and children with disabilities will ensure their full participation in society.

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